

Awareness, Information Literacy Skill and Cloud School Management Use by Public Secondary Schools in Osun State

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Abstract

In recent times, effective use of electronic information resources depends on the level of awareness, literacy skills, and others. However, this study was conducted to determine whether or not awareness and information literacy skills as determinants that influence the use of cloud school management systematic by students and teachers in Public secondary schools in Osun State, both directly and indirectly. Multistage sampling technique of random technique to select one Local Government Area from a senatorial district while purposive sampling was adopted to select respondents of 11,022 comprised of 430 teachers and 10,592 students. The questionnaires were administered to the identified respondents but 10,143 questionnaires were retrieved for analysis. The results of the study revealed a strong association between the variables with a correlation ranging between $r = 0.802$ to $r = 0.921$. Awareness has a significant positive correlation with Information Literacy skills, and Cloud School Management use with Pearson correlation of 0.92, and 0.802 respectively at $p < 0.01$. Information Literacy skill has a significant relationship with awareness, and Cloud School Management use with correlation ranging from $r = 0.921$ to $r = 0.810$. Cloud School Management use, awareness, and Information Literacy skills has a strong significant positive relationship with $r = 0.802$ to $r = 0.810$ at $p < 0.01$. Following the results, the author concludes that the ability of the students to efficiently and effectively utilise electronic information resources efficiently to meet their information needs is inadequate. It was also recommended that seminars and workshops be organised to sensitise and quipped the students and teachers respectively. This will be strengthening teachers' and students' capacities to manage and utilise resources and services effectively. Information literacy and skill should also be incorporated included into secondary schools' curricula.

Keywords: Awareness, Information literacy skill, Cloud school management

Introduction

In the past decade, there has been a paradigm shift from paper-based to net-based electronic knowledge for teaching and learning effectiveness. Electronic information resources consist of data representing numbers, text, graphics, images, maps, moving images, music, sounds, etc., and programs of instruction sets. Before the development of Computer and Internet Technology, printed versions of resources such as books, journals, dictionaries, and workbooks, among others, played a significant role in the teaching and learning process.

Cloud school management (CSM) is an independent variable in this study. CSM can be described as an electronic information resource purposely developed and deployed to support and enhance the effectiveness of an educational system of a Secondary school's teaching and learning process. The resources make use of internet facilities and can be accessed anywhere and by teachers and students or other users at the same time, which makes it very convenient to use.

Moreover, CSM is used in searching for literature on specialised subjects and looking for relevant information in related subjects or fields. The resource is equally used for study and updates in subject information, research and development activities, and assignments. Cloud School Management is characterised by flexibility, portability, and searching facilities access/ dissemination are benefits in terms of time and space. Interestingly, the most adopted method to learn to use cloud school management is self-learning or self-teaching. Therefore, the use of CSM in the education system is of great necessity to students at all levels especially the secondary school and their teachers because they provide better, faster, and easier access to information than information accessed through print media. In addition, CSM helps secondary school students and teachers to increase accessibility, improve usability and effectiveness; establish a new way for students to use information in a more productive and effective in

their academic activities; and keep them abreast with current developments in teaching and learning (Khalil, 2014). Thus, CSM is an electronic information resource that deals with born electronic and digitised materials which can be either accessible through a designated a world-wide-web address.

Awareness could be referred to as knowledge about something that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at present based on information or experience (Akpojotor, 2016). It can also be described as knowledge or perception of a situation, fact, consciousness, recognition, realisation, grasp, and acknowledgment of concern about and well-informed interest or familiarity in a particular situation or development. Thus, awareness of electronic resources is of paramount importance to education efficiency and effectiveness at all levels in this 21st century. According to Prangya and Rabindra (2013), awareness is core to the usage of electronic information resources. It was also stated by the authors that where materials are in closed access, users' ease of access to such e-resources is by far reduced. But where they are in open access (not subscription-based), students find them and make do with them for whatever reasons they need them. The usage of Electronic information resources in recent years has yielded positive results in the area of teaching and research and through the use of electronic information resources, researchers, academics, and students now have access to global information resources, particularly the Internet for their scholarly intercourse (Egberongbe, 2011; Gakibayo et al., 2013). Thus, awareness of the students and teachers is of great importance to the frequency of using the available resources, and cloud school management. However, if potential users are not aware of the resources, the patronage of the resource will be lower than the expected level of resource utilisation.

First and foremost, there is a need to understand the term Information literacy before describing what the variable information literacy skill is. This is because, for a person to be information literate, he/she must be able to recognise when information is needed and can locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information. Ndagi (2018) stated that information literacy is the ability to locate, evaluate and use effectively the needed information. It was also described as the ability of a person to locate, evaluate, manage, and use information from a range of sources not only for problem-solving but also for decision-making and research (Ojedokun & Lumade, 2015). Thus, an information-literate person can effectively access, evaluate, organise, synthesise, and apply information from a variety of sources and formats in a variety of contexts to be able to achieve its intended use.

In addition, the ability for a student to be able to select, retrieve and use library resources requires information literacy skills where a user has to be able to define information tasks, locate and access information, use information, synthesise information from different sources, and evaluate information to be able to use the information and solve a given task. Therefore, students require different technical skills such as the skills to select the information needed, locate information, retrieve useful information, evaluate information, and use information appropriately to complete a specified task (Nwezeh, 2011). These changes have made information literacy to be recognised as a critical tool for the 21st century (Adeyemi, 2017) and it was suggested that secondary school students should be information literate for them to succeed in their academic endeavours. Information literacy is a tool for individual empowerment and community development. Therefore, it is important to equip information users, especially secondary school students within the context of this study with information literacy skills to help them know when they need information, access, evaluate and use it ethically and morally in the construction of individual knowledge for immediate and lifelong learning.

Moreover, scholars such as Adeyemi (2017), Zulkifpeli et al. (2016) and Malliari et al. (2014) have recognised the significance of information literacy in schools contending that information literacy is of value in every aspect of a human being and a prerequisite in the learning process at all levels. Information literacy skills are important for secondary school students for successful learning in an information-rich future. Therefore, students experience a range of information-related problems including the use of low-quality information, information overload,

and inability to find the needed information if they lack the necessary skills to search, locate, process, evaluate and use information (Anyaku et al., 2015). Based on this, as cited by Momanyi (2018), some of the available electronic information resources have not been utilised at all.

Statement of the problem

Information literacy is essential for information users at all levels especially public secondary schools teachers and students in the knowledge economy as it equips them with skills to know when and where to locate information. Teachers and students in secondary school need Information literacy and skills to help them supplement classroom teaching and learning with information that they can access and use appropriately.

It may be unclear to some of the stakeholders how information users in secondary school navigate through the deluge of information to achieve their goals. And it was discovered from various literature that people have experienced a wide range of information-related problems including the use of low-quality information, information overload, and inability to find the needed information if they lack the necessary skills to search, locate, process, evaluate and use information. In light of the above, the study examined awareness, information literacy skills, and cloud school management use by teachers and students in public secondary schools in Osun State.

Research questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of awareness of cloud school management by teachers and students in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria?
2. What is the degree of the information literacy skills of teachers and students in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria?
3. Do awareness and information literacy skills influence the use of cloud schools management by teachers and students in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria?

Research hypothesis

The null hypothesis that was tested at a 0.05 level of significance is as follows:

1. Awareness and information literacy skills do not significantly, jointly influence cloud school management by the teachers and students of public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria.

Review of related literature

Below are some of the notable studies on awareness, technology adoption, and information literacy skills as it affects the use of electronic resources utilisation.

Ekong and Ekong (2018) study the impact of information literacy skills on the use of e-library resources among tertiary institution students in Akwa Ibom State. The survey design was used for this research. A total of 500 questionnaires were administered, out of which, 450 (90.0%) were returned. The study revealed that most of the respondents lacked the necessary computer literacy skills in using e-library resources and other internet technologies which have affected the use of e-library resources. It was also gathered that students make better grades when they use computers, e-resources, and other IT technologies when doing their assignments and research thereby improving their academic performance.

According to research conducted by Aina (2014), the study was on awareness, accessibility, and use of electronic databases among the academic staff of Babcock University. It was discovered that 69.4% of the respondents were aware of Academic Journal. It was therefore concluded that nine out of thirteen databases under consideration were averagely aware by respondents. This implies that there is a need to increase awareness to cover all the electronic resources being subscribed to by the library.

Theoretical framework

The study shall be hinged on the theory of diffusion of Innovation (DOI) and the technology acceptance model. The review is as presented;

Technology acceptance model (TAM)

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Davis in (1989). The objective of TAM was to shed light on the processes supporting the acceptance of and use of technology. According to TAM, technology acceptance is a process, whereby external factors such as features of the system trigger cognitive responses (perceived-ease-of-use and perceived usefulness), which, in turn, influence individual behaviour.

Based on prior empirical literature on human behaviour and the management of information systems, multi-item scales for perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness were developed, pre-tested, and validated in several studies. It was hypothesised that the two constructs were fundamental determinants of user acceptance, due to evidence in previous research. The research suggested that an individual's decision to perform a particular behaviour is the result of the analysis of the benefit that they expect to receive from the behaviour compared to the effort/costs they put in to perform the behaviour (cited by Ajibade, 2018). This means that the use of the information system is determined by an evaluation of the trade-off between the perceived usefulness of the system and the perceived difficulty of using it (Davis, 1989).

Moreover, TAM does not consider factors such as age and education as external variables which could influence acceptance of and willingness to use technology. Accordingly, potential users of technology may not necessarily base their acceptance of and willingness to use new technology on their perceptions of the usefulness of IT and how easy it is to use, although the model does suggest that there may be other external factors that could be responsible for their acceptance of the technology (Zahid et al., 2013). With regards to the use of cloud school management, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were found to have a direct influence on behaviour intention, thus eliminating the need for the attitude construct.

Diffusion of innovation theory

The diffusion of innovation (DOI) theory was coined by Rogers in the year (1962). The theory has been defined as the diffusion of new ideas, behaviours, or technology within a social system. The theory assumes that individuals embrace a new idea, habit, product, or technology as part of the social system. It is concerned with the spread of ideas through several channels throughout time.

The theorist further asserted that relative benefit, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability constitute the primary criteria for innovation uptake. The extent to which innovation is considered superior to the programme, product, or idea it replaces is referred to as relative advantage. The degree to which innovation is compatible with the experiences, values, and requirements of possible adopters is referred to as compatibility. The complexity of innovation refers to how difficult it is to comprehend and/or implement. Trialability refers to how well an innovation can be tested or explored before committing to adopt it, while observability refers to how well it produces tangible outcomes.

The DOI research had a considerable positive impact on information system (IS) research. Its models were process-based, contextual, and non-deterministic, and could identify necessary conditions for adoption. However, DOI theory does not offer adequate constructs to deal with collective adoption behaviours including the critical role of standards, critical mass, network externalities, sunk costs, path dependence, and others. It is assumed that the adoption of CSM in public secondary schools would lead to improved teaching and learning processes, flexibility, efficiency, faster service development, and delivery, and fostering of cross-team collaboration in the education system.

Methodology

Multi stages sampling techniques were adopted. The first stage involves the use of systematic random sampling through which one Local Government Area was selected from each senatorial district while the purposive sampling method was used to select a total of 37 secondary schools comprising 430 teachers and 10,592 students upon which questionnaires were administered. A detailed summary is shown below:

Local Government	Number of Secondary School	Number of Teachers
Ayedaade	19	119
Ede North	6	137
Ifelodun	12	174
Total	37	430
<u>10,592</u>		

Source: Ministry of Education, Osun State, 2022

In summary, the total number of questionnaires administered was 11,022, out of which 10,143 (Teachers: 430, Students: 9,713) were retrieved for further processing. This represents 92.2% of the administered questionnaires. The exercise was conducted between December 2022 and January 2023. In carrying out this project work, questionnaires were drawn to gather information from both the Teachers and Students of public Secondary schools in three selected Local Government Areas of Ayedaade, Ede North, and Ifelodun. Eleven thousand and twenty two copies of the questionnaire (close-ended ones) were employed to obtain useful information for the study.

Reliability test

Reliability refers to the degree to which consequences are steady over time. Reliability is required in research studies. This study uses a coefficient alpha to estimate internal consistency reliability. Cronbach’s alpha, which is also known as alpha reliability is a method of examining the reliability of the designed tools to be used for the study. The researcher used this method to examine the internal consistency of the items with the use of SPSS 20 using Unity School, Ejigbo of a population of 105 (teachers are 32 and students are 73). The school was not among the secondary schools selected for the study. The Cronbach’s alpha for this study was 0.904, which is statistically reliable for me to proceed with the analysis.

Testing of hypothesis

Correlation analysis result presentation

Correlation Analysis Result Presentation to test Hypothesis, Positive correlation exists between awareness, Information Literacy Skills, and the use of Cloud School Management by the teachers and students of Public secondary schools in Osun State.

Table 2: Regression analysis of hypothesis

School Management		Awareness	Information Literacy Skill Cloud
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1.000	0.921**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
	0.802**		
	0.000		

	N	10,143	10,143
10,143			
Information	Pearson Correlation	0.921**	1.000
0.810**			
Literacy Skills	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
0.000			
	N	10,143	10,143
10,143			
Cloud School	Pearson Correlation	0.802**	0.810**
0.810**			
Management	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
0.000			
	N	10,143	10,143
10,143			

Source: Survey result, 2023

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted between the variables to establish the relationship between the variables. In this study, coefficient correlation (r) was used to determine if there were positive or negative relationships between the variables under study. A correlation analysis is used to examine if there is an association between two variables or whether there is an observed covariance between two variables of interest (Howell, 2013). The correlation coefficient ranges between -1 and 1. The coefficient which is close to +1 or -1 indicates that there is a strong linear relationship between the two variables. The results of the correlation coefficient for this study are indicated in Table 4.

Result interpretation

Correlation between independent variables ranged between $r = 0.802$ to $r = 0.921$. The highest correlation between the independent variable was observed between awareness, Information Literacy skills, and cloud school management use, indicating a strong association between the variables. The result revealed that,

- i. Awareness has a significant positive correlation with Information Literacy skills, and Cloud School Management use with Pearson correlation of 0.92, and 0.802 respectively at $p < 0.0$. This finding was in line with Prangya and Rabindra (2013) that with the usage of electronic information resources, the quality of the student research work improves with the enrichment of appurtenant contents and materials leading to high-quality manuscripts;
- ii. Information Literacy skills have a significant relationship with awareness, and Cloud School Management use. The observed critical values (2-tailed) of the correlation between the dependent variable and the independent variable ranged from $r = 0.921$ to $r = 0.810$. These results indicate that information literacy skills had a great positive effect on the use of Cloud School Management. This is an assertion to the study conducted by Ekong & Ekong (2018) which revealed that the quality and volume of academic work are largely influenced by the knowledge and skills possessed in the use of e-library resources; and
- iii. Cloud School Management use, awareness, and Information Literacy skills has a strong significant positive relationship with $r = 0.802$ to $r = 0.810$ at $p < 0.01$. The finding of this study is in tandem with the findings of Sivathaasan and Velnampy (2013) who found that the use of electronic resources has improved the academic performance of teachers at the University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka.

Conclusion

There is an indication that most of the secondary school teachers and students of the selected secondary schools in Osun State are aware of the implemented Cloud School Management, and they make use of them to the best of their knowledge, ability, and capability. However, the ability of the

students in secondary schools to efficiently and effectively utilise electronic resources in searching for the required information is not adequate i.e. the skills in searching for the Information needed are adequate. The students relied on teachers' help to understand class assignments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. The school authority should create more awareness of the use of Cloud School Management among students at the Senior secondary school level by conducting workshops, and seminars;
- ii. Secondary schools in the State should be provided with the latest computer and peripheral devices, with good and reliable antivirus software that will always secure the library resources. With the advances in Information Technology desktop computers should be supplemented with laptops so the teachers have more library spaces to cater to more users; and
- iii. students should be trained on how to use electronic information resources that are available in the State.

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